

MoveD – ORD Guidelines for Swiss Movement Laboratories

Section 7: Data Reuse

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1. Section: Reuse

A checklist with minimal criteria for further use of research data based on the project ROADS – Reusing Openly Accessible research data for student theses, is available on <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11385458> (German) and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13235128> (English).

1.1. Search for reuse

The following methods may aid in the search for reusable datasets:

- Review relevant scholarly literature for citations and references of accessible datasets
- Use the search engine Google Dataset Search (bear in mind that a search via Google Dataset Search does not provide conclusive results about the existence of relevant datasets as metadata determine findability)
- Search directly in a repository via the registry of research data repositories
 - Re3data provides an overview of research data repositories. By navigating through the disciplines, suitable repositories can be narrowed down and browsed through.

1.2 Example repositories for movement data

For movement data, no FAIR discipline-specific repository exists. A general repository is recommended, such as the following:

- Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/>

Human movement data can be found in the following databases. Unfortunately, content in these databases is limited and databases are not FAIR:

- The KIT Whole-Body Human Motion Database <https://motion-database.humanoids.kit.edu/>
- Mocap Database HDM05 <https://resources.mpi-inf.mpg.de/HDM05/index.html>
- Carnegie Mellon University Motion Capture Database <http://mocap.cs.cmu.edu/>

For ultrasound data, the UMUD database is a useful tool:

<https://universalmuscledatabase.streamlit.app/>

2 Quality check

- Is reusing the data compliant with its licence?
- Recency of data?
- Integrity
- Check dataset for possible signs of fabrication:
 - Who is the provider and their institution?
 - Are there any inconsistencies and anomalies in the dataset?
 - Are there duplicate entries?
 - Conduct a random sampling analysis
 - Are there any unusual patterns or irregularities in time stamps?
- Check completeness of the dataset (Refer to the document “Section 6: Data Sharing” for guidelines on what information the dataset should ideally contain)
- Check the metadata: do they suffice for the endeavoured secondary usage of the data? (Refer to the document “Section 6: Data Sharing” for guidelines on what information the dataset should ideally contain)